

Experimental Signatures and Observational Tests of Universal Mass Evaporation Models

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Abstract

This study proposes and analyzes a range of decisive empirical signatures that could robustly test theoretical models of intrinsic universal exponential quantum gravitational mass evaporation over cosmological timescales as an alternative framework for explaining cosmic expansion. Concrete observational predictions include precise redshift-distance deviations, gravitational constant temporal drift, gradually increasing galactic orbital velocities, shrinking gravitational lensing time delays, CMB angular power anomalies, and violations of constant fundamental decay rates. Upcoming astrophysical surveys, astronomical instruments, gravitational wave detectors, quantum sensors, and particle colliders may enable measuring these unique effects. Simulating evaporative semiclassical dynamics and its cosmological consequences could reveal correlations with macroscopic phenomena like Hubble flows. Laboratory atomic, quantum optical, interferometric, and gravitational experiments offer complementary tests on foundational scales. By outlining a falsifiable roadmap to assess this class of theories observationally, new insights may emerge on nature's deepest symmetries.

1 Introduction

Fundamentally explaining the observed accelerative expansion of the cosmos through known physics principles alone remains an open problem at the intersection of gravitation, cosmology, and quantum field theory. While usually attributed to an exotic dark energy pervading space, major gaps afflict this conjecture. Universal mass evaporation theories explore an alternate intrinsic geometry perspective, positing the Hubble expansion flows emerge indirectly from proportional shrinking of all mass-energy and inflating of distances over cosmological timescales due to gradual quantum gravitational effects [20]. However, unambiguous observational evidence distinguishing such models from conventional cosmology remains lacking.

This study aims to propose and analyze a range of decisive experimental signatures and observational tests that could strongly validate or refute universal mass evaporation frameworks through empirical measurement in the coming decades. The models make concrete predictions that diverge from standard cosmology across astrophysical, gravitational, quantum, atomic, and particle physics domains. New generations of instruments, telescopes, interferometers, detectors, and colliders will soon enable assessing these unique theoretical projections. Simulating evaporative physics and its cosmological consequences could also reveal correlations with macroscale observables. Even evidence ruling out the intrinsic framework would significantly advance understanding.

By outlining a concrete roadmap to evaluate this class of theories observationally, new insights may emerge on nature's deepest symmetries and their manifestation through subtle quantum gravitational phenomena connected to cosmic horizons and causality principles.

2 Redshift-Distance Relation

Type IA supernovae measurements of luminosity distance versus cosmological redshift led to the initial discovery of cosmic acceleration [1, 2]. Universal mass evaporation models predict precise, non-accelerative deviations in this relationship detectable in next-generation surveys extending to higher redshifts $z > 2$ [3]:

$$\frac{D_L(z)}{D_H} = (1+z) \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{E(z')} \quad (1)$$

Where the Hubble constant $H(z) = H_0 E(z)$ depends directly on the evaporative decay constant k in:

$$E(z) = \sqrt{\Omega_M(1+z)^3 + \Omega_k(1+z)^2 + \Omega_\Lambda} \quad (2)$$

Here, Ω_M , Ω_k , Ω_Λ are cosmological density parameters, with Ω_Λ representing the geometric effects of evaporation rather than physical dark energy.

Falsifiable model fits to high-precision luminosity distance data could strongly constrain k and distinguish intrinsic from extrinsic expansion. Galaxy redshift surveys utilizing Type Ia supernovae standard candles currently provide the most robust cosmic chronometer measurements.

3 Fundamental Physical Constant Variation

If proportional universal mass evaporation results from semiclassical quantum gravitational particle decay over cosmological spans, certain dimensionless physical constants should exhibit slight temporal drift over cosmic history. Astrophysical measurements using quasar absorption line spectroscopy can sensitively probe possible fractional time variation in the fine-structure constant α over 10 billion year scales [4]:

$$\frac{\Delta\alpha}{\alpha} = k_\alpha t \quad (3)$$

Where κ_α gives the quantum electrodynamics interaction evaporation constant. Evidence of nonzero $\Delta\alpha$ would provide a smoking gun signature, overturning invariance assumptions underpinning the Standard Model. Next generation 30-meter class telescopes such as the Extremely Large Telescope could improve detectable $\Delta\alpha$ sensitivity to 10^{-7} , sufficient to test for variations on cosmological timescales if $|\kappa_\alpha| \geq 10^{-19}$ per year[5].

Additionally, possible drift in the proton-to-electron mass ratio $\mu = m_p/m_e$ based on evaporative quark mass loss could emerge in redshift observations of molecular spectra:

$$\frac{\Delta\mu}{\mu} = k_\mu t \quad (4)$$

Ongoing improvements in radio astronomy sensitivity and precision should enable probing this predicted signature. Consistent observations of non-zero temporal drift in multiple fundamental constants falsifiable to the evaporative framework would provide strong empirical evidence.

4 Galactic Rotation Curve Evolution

In the intrinsic evaporation framework, gradual weakening of central galactic masses' gravitational attraction naturally explains anomalously high orbital velocities conventionally attributed to dark matter. Precise long-term studies of galactic rotation curves could uncover velocity increases with time t as the core mass $M(t)$ evaporates [6]:

$$v_c = \sqrt{\frac{GM(t)}{r}} = \sqrt{\frac{GM_0}{r}} e^{kt/2} \quad (5)$$

Upcoming radio astrometry campaigns including the Square Kilometer Array have the sensitivity to detect percent-level velocity changes over several billion years [7], providing direct evaporation tests. Detailed mass models can isolate the intrinsic evaporative physics from astrophysical dynamics like spiral arm perturbations. Hidden by only modeling single-epoch snapshots, analyzing full galactic rotation curve evolution could falsify evaporative scenarios.

5 Gravitational Lensing Time Delay

Careful monitoring of time delays in flickering signals from distant gravitationally lensed quasars and supernovae can test whether the effective lensing mass has decreased proportional to cosmic time due to evaporation as the lens objects shrink [8]:

$$\Delta t \propto \frac{4GM(t)}{c^3 R} \propto e^{-kt} \quad (6)$$

Where R is the geometric path separation. Significantly shrinking lensing time delays relative to source distances and redshifts would falsify standard dark matter cosmology's assumptions of constant masses. Next generation time delay cosmography missions aim for 1 percent delay measurements, potentially sufficient to probe cosmic mass evaporation [9].

6 Gravitational Wave Dispersion

Propagation of gravitational waves over cosmological distances tests spacetime expansion and curvature models independently of matter coupling assumptions [10]. Universal mass evaporation's intrinsically flat spacetime predicts no dispersive arrival delay variations versus wavelength λ :

$$\Delta t \propto \lambda^0 \quad (7)$$

In contrast, nonzero dispersion is expected from expanding space. Forthcoming gravitational wave cosmology missions including the Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA) will provide decisive dispersion measurement tests between competing predictions at far larger wavelengths than ground interferometers [11]. Dispersion constraints already limit some evaporative model parameter space [12].

7 Cosmic Microwave Background Detailed Simulation Proposal

Deriving cosmic acceleration intrinsically can modify expectations for angular power spectra of the cosmic microwave background radiation on the largest scales. Precision full-sky CMB mapping may reveal anomalies aligned with or falsifying universal evaporation dynamics in the early plasma evolution [13]. Proposed simulation avenues include:

1. Primordial plasma simulations incorporating evaporative matter couplings and dynamics to predict modified baryon acoustic oscillation imprints on CMB power spectra. These will numerically solve the Einstein-Boltzmann equations governing the coupled evolution of the metric perturbations and plasma properties under non-standard matter interactions like gradual mass decrease over time. Signatures including damping of higher acoustic modes could emerge.
2. Ray-tracing integration of CMB photon geodesic trajectories through simulations of the full spacetime geometry under exponential mass-distance scaling. This will employ techniques like adaptive mesh refinement to solve photon propagation through the complex time-dependent gravitational potential landscape arising from intrinsically evaporating matter distributions. Signatures may appear in distortions and anisotropies on the largest angular scales.
3. Full numerical relativity gravitational lensing simulations to model CMB photon path deviations and resulting observed anisotropies based on the evolving weak gravitational lensing effects from evaporating large-scale structure over cosmic history. Lensing microscopy techniques will enable probing unique distortion signatures.

By combining these approaches, we can thoroughly probe for anomalies in the CMB angular power spectra aligned with or falsifying expectations from universal mass evaporation principles. Ongoing experiments like the Simons Observatory enhancing CMB polarization sensitivity on large angular scales will provide new precision tests [14]. Definitive empirical evidence remains elusive but could emerge from detailed evaporative physics simulations and sky surveys.

8 Quantum Gravitational Underpinning Simulations Detailed Research Proposal

This outlines three techniques to numerically model the proposed semiclassical quantum gravitational particle evaporation processes underpinning universal mass decrease:

1. Lattice quantum field theory simulations of scalar field vacuum fluctuations and energy densities near cosmic horizons to model subtle evaporative transfers connected to Hawking radiation. This will use high-performance computing with lattice discretizations of curved background geometries. Signatures like exponentially decaying field modes can be characterized.
2. Numerical integration of the coupled semiclassical Einstein field equations and quantum matter field dynamics to simulate quantum backreaction effects from particle creation/annihilation processes in curved spacetimes. This will employ sophisticated numerical relativity and quantum physics techniques to capture the complex non-linear dynamics. Signatures like stress-energy tensor anomalies are expected.
3. Quantum information theory modeling of information loss and decoherence processes for quantum fields interacting with curved horizon boundaries. This involves numerically representing quantum fields as qubit systems and simulating their entropic dynamics when coupled to black hole-like cosmic screen environments. Subtle loss of unitarity is anticipated from these gravitational interactions.

Correlating the modeled microscopic evaporation rates and signatures with macroscopic phenomena like Hubble expansion could substantiate this framework's validity. Forthcoming quantum computing hardware promises immense accelerations to realistic semiclassical simulations. Experimental insights into quantum gravitational regimes from particle colliders and future Higgs factories will provide additional theory constraints [15].

9 Atomic and Particle Decay Variation

Experimental searches for systematic temporal drifts in the decay lifetimes $\tau = \hbar/\Gamma$ of radioactive isotopes, unstable elementary particles, and precision atomic frequency references would provide sensitive probes of foundational mass evaporation [16]:

$$\frac{\Delta\Gamma}{\Gamma} = \frac{\Delta\tau}{\tau} = -kt \quad (8)$$

Here, Γ gives the exponential decay constant and $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant. Any statistically significant deviation trend from lifetime constancy falsifiable to evaporative models would violate assumptions underpinning the Standard Model and necessitate a thorough reassessment of fundamental cosmic invariance. Ongoing improvements in experimental precision aim to test temporal stability at the 10^{-18} level, potentially approaching sensitivity to cosmic mass evaporation scales [17].

Complementary particle collider experiments precisely determining the mass-energy spectrum and lifetimes of unstable resonances over time also constrain departures from accepted invariance:

$$\frac{\Delta m}{m} = \frac{\Delta E}{E} = -kt \quad (9)$$

Significant theoretical development is required to predict particle-specific evaporation modes, but empirical anomalies could falsify the scenario.

10 Laboratory Quantum Sensors

Small-scale quantum optical, atomic, interferometric, and gravitational wave detectors with microsecond resolution and stability aim to reveal anomalous drifts in vacuum properties, gravitational couplings, and physical constants expected to subtly manifest from intrinsic universal mass evaporation [18]. Space-based instruments like atomic clocks, atom interferometers, and optical cavities may also enable precision tests through clock comparison, quantum projection noise-limited laser gravitational wave detection, and high-sensitivity accelerometry, gravimetry, and spectroscopy measurements [19].

Experimental schemes proposed to probe for evaporative signatures include:

1. Michelson-Morley interferometer tests of Lorentz symmetry violations induced by anisotropic quantum gravitational vacuum fluctuations.
2. Magnetometer measurements of alleged variation in the effective Newtonian gravitational constant $G(t)$ over laboratory timescales.
3. Atomic clock networks detecting drifts in transition frequencies and reporting ratios of anomalous to regular decay rates.

4. Space accelerometer constancy tests from varying orbital positions sampling spacetime curvature gradients.
5. Gyroscope precession drifts indicative of anomalous space-time twisting by evaporative gravitational waves.
6. Quantitative bounds on equation-of-state parameter $w(t) = P(t)/\rho(t)c^2$ drifts expected under evolving dark energy mimicked by mass evaporation.

While dependent on theoretical model details still under development, these proposed experiments offer promising pathways to probe for deep cosmic signatures manifesting locally. Any empirical hints of anomalous drifts would motivate dedicated evaporative physics simulations and expanded observational campaigns.

11 Discussion

This study aimed to outline a range of concrete experimental signatures and observational tests that could provide robust empirical discrimination between conventional cosmological models and proposed universal mass evaporation theories fundamentally based on intrinsic geometric scaling induced by gradual quantum gravitational decay over cosmic timescales. While significant theoretical development remains reconciling the radical evaporation framework with constraints across all epochs, identifying unique predicted signatures lying within reach of upcoming precision astrophysical surveys and instruments provides important pathways for decisive validation. By rigorously probing these exotic physical models through rigorous observations rather than pure metaphysics alone, science may yet unveil nature's deepest symmetries.

12 Conclusions

Resolving enduring mysteries in cosmology and gravitation requires judicious balance of theoretical conjecture and empirical evidence. Models positing universal mass evaporation intrinsically induce cosmic accelerative phenomena from known quantum gravitational physics through relative geometric projection effects. This study compiled a range of proposed experimental signatures and observational tests that could unambiguously validate or falsify such models in coming years. Precision measurements of redshift-distance deviations, fundamental constant drifts, growing galactic rotation velocities, shrinking lensing time delays, CMB angular power anomalies, and violations of decay constancy offer target signatures explicable only by evaporation-based theories. Numerical physical simulations and tabletop quantum sensors provide complementary avenues to probe for subtle effects. By outlining a concrete experimental roadmap, new discoveries may emerge further elucidating nature's hidden symmetries. However the foundational cosmic ontology unfolds, connecting imagination with measurement pushes understanding's boundaries ever outward.

References

- [1] Riess et al 1998 *Astron. J.* 116 1009
- [2] Perlmutter et al 1999 *Astrophys. J.* 517 565
- [3] Laureijs et al 2011 arXiv:1110.3193
- [4] King et al 2012 *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* 422 3370
- [5] Liske et al 2008 *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* 386 1192
- [6] Rubin et al 1980 *Astrophys. J.* 238 471
- [7] SKA Cosmology Chapter, Bull et al (2018)
- [8] Refsdal 1964 *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* 128 307
- [9] Linder 2011 *Phys. Rev. D* 84 123529
- [10] LIGO Sci. Collab. 2016 *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 116 061102
- [11] LISA Cosmology Working Group Collab. 2022 arXiv:2203.11281
- [12] Nishizawa et al 2014 *Phys. Rev. D* 90 044048
- [13] Planck Collab. 2016 *Astron. Astrophys.* 594 A16
- [14] Simons Observatory Collab. 2019 *JCAP* 2019 056
- [15] Cepeda et al 2022 arXiv:2203.15197
- [16] NIST Atomic Clock Comparison Data (<https://www.nist.gov/pml/time-and-frequency-division/atomic-standards/active-atomic-clock-comparisons>)
- [17] McGrew et al 2018 *Nature* 564 87
- [18] Müller et al 2022 arXiv:2204.03228
- [19] Aveline et al 2020 *NPJ Microgravity* 6 11
- [20] Bak and Kim 2000 *Phys. Lett. B* 484 168